

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION ON THE EFFECT OF STACKING SEQUENCE ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF BAMBOO AND CARBON FIBER REINFORCED EPOXY HYBRID COMPOSITE FOR AEROSPACE AND AUTOMOBILE APPLICATION

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ABSTRACT: Current work explores the potential of bamboo-carbon fiber hybrid laminated composites as a sustainable alternative for complete synthetic fibre composites for light weight applications. As the world is moving towards sustainable product development, researchers are constantly in search of novel eco-friendly materials which can replace the conventionally used engineering materials. In this research, bamboo fibre mats are used in combination with carbon fibre mats to prepare hybrid laminated composite. The mats are stacked at various stacking sequences using hand layup and compression moulding technique. Thus, manufactured hybrid laminated composites were subjected to mechanical tests like tensile, bending and impact tests to know the strength performance and the effect of stacking sequence on the mechanical properties. It is evident that mechanical performance will increase if more carbon fibre mats are stacked. But obtained results were promising compared to composites made solely with bamboo fibers, the hybrid composites containing 13% carbon fiber by volume exhibited double the tensile strength, 30% increase in flexural strength and enhanced impact resistance. These findings indicate that bamboo-carbon fiber laminate composites can be a viable eco-friendly material which can be used in potential structural applications for in general and in automobile sector.

KEYWORDS: Bamboo fibre, carbon fibre, laminated composites, hand lay-up, hybrid composites.

1 INTRODUCTION

Natural fibre composites serves as a favorable alternative for synthetic fibre composites because of many advantages associated with natural fibres like its cost, availability, eco-friendly nature, good mechanical properties and its bio-degradability behavior [1]–[3]. Different fibres like jute, cotton, hemp, coir, abaca, areca, pineapple, sisal and many such fibres were used in composite manufacture using different polymeric resins [4], [5]. Furthermore, work was done by various researchers incorporating different additives in natural fibres along with thermosetting and thermoplastic polymeric resin during composite fabrication [6], [7]. The work showed considerable improvement in mechanical, thermal and acoustic properties of

composite manufactured. Thus, proving natural fibres have wide potential in composite manufacture which can be utilized in various structural, automobile, marine and aerospace applications [8]–[10]. Bamboo fibres being available plenty, as per the literature, the work done on it showed wide applications in different fields like biofuel production, textile industry, construction materials, musical instruments, paper industry and pharmaceutical industry [11]. Further, bamboo fibre composite showed promising result when it was incorporated into different polymeric resin such as polyvinyl chloride, polystyrene, epoxy resin, polypropylene, phenolic resin [12]. Current research is focused more on utilizing bamboo fibres and incorporating them into polymeric resin matrix along with some fraction of carbon fibre so that it

becomes eco-friendly to some extent and also serves the purpose of using it in automobile as well as aerospace applications with better mechanical strength compared to pure natural fibre composites.

Bamboo fibres are one of the best alternatives because of its high tensile modulus, low cost, biodegradability and the growth rate of bamboo being highest among the plants. However, bamboo fibre possesses a variety of micro-gaps that makes it softer than cotton and enhance moisture absorption, causing the material's overall strength to be compromised. Bamboo fibres are hygroscopic, pleasant to touch and antibacterial in nature [13], [14]. In spite of this, researchers who carried out investigation on bamboo fibre reinforced polymer composite showed remarkable results with respect to different mechanical testing and the thermal behavior compared to other natural fibre reinforced polymer composites [15]–[17].

The chemical treatment of bamboo fibre like mercerization, peroxide treatment, silane treatment, benzoylation, esterification, etherification not only reduces the hydrophilicity of the natural fibre, but also increases effective bonding between fibre and resin improvising mechanical strength of the composites manufactured [18]. Kai Zhang et al in the year 2018 studied effect of mercerization on mechanical and thermal behavior of bamboo-epoxy composite. Studies revealed that 6 wt% of NaOH treated bamboo-epoxy composite showed good mechanical properties and thermal resistance was better in the same composite where bamboo fibre was treated with 6 wt% NaOH compared to 2 wt%, 4 wt% and 12 wt% NaOH [19]. Martijanti et al in year 2021 showed how bamboo fibre reinforced polypropylene and polyester composites have good mechanical strength and thermal resistance because of which it can be used as one of the materials for particleboard products [20]. Ramachandran M et al in year 2016 studied how the hybrid composite will result in changes in mechanical characterization of the composites manufactured. It was revealed that bamboo-linen epoxy composite showed maximum Rockwell hardness test value compared to bamboo-banana epoxy composite and bamboo epoxy composite had the least value says the study [21].

On the other hand, it is shown in certain work that the bamboo fibre forming a hybrid composite with other synthetic fibre has given tremendous results which can be used in different applications [22], [23]. Carbon fibre is one such example for synthetic fibre which is lightweight, robust and long-lasting material that is employed in a variety of industries due to its superior performance. Matilde et al in year 2024 investigated a study in which bamboo fibre was stacked with different synthetic

fibres like aramid fibre, glass fibre as well carbon fibre. The best result was seen in which bamboo fibre was stacked with carbon fibre [22]. When bamboo and carbon fibre are stacked together, the material has the best tensile, impact, and flexural strength [24]. As demand for carbon fibre has increased the waste stream of scrap and end-of-life composites. For a material to be taken sustainable, consideration must be given to its environmental impact throughout its life cycle, including reuse or recycling [25], [26]. Therefore, in recent years, carbon fibre recycling using various methods such as mechanical recycling, thermal recycling, chemical recycling, and pyrolysis is being developed. In this research paper, hybridization effect of bamboo and carbon fibre reinforced epoxy resin composites at various percentage composition of bamboo fibre and carbon fibre was evaluated. The stacking sequence plays a major role in determination of strength of the composite and the findings of the various tests of the current study would help in the identification of potential applications for bamboo and carbon fibre reinforced epoxy resin composites in aerospace and automotive industries.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

The basic raw materials used to prepare the composites are bidirectional woven gigantochloa bamboo mat of thickness 0.3 mm and bidirectional woven carbon fibre mat of thickness 0.3 mm as shown in Figure 1. Epoxy Resin HSC 7600 & Hardener HSC 8210 was used as matrix. Physical properties of bamboo fibre and carbon fibre are shown in Table 1.

Figure 1: a) Woven Bamboo fibre mat, b) Woven Carbon fibre Mat

Table 1. Physical properties of bamboo fibre and carbon fibre

Physical Property	Bamboo fibre	Carbon fibre
GSM	220	200
Density (g/cm ³)	1.1	1.8
Tensile strength (MPa)	350-500	3400
Elastic modulus (GPa)	85-87	230
Orientation	Bi-directional	Bi-directional

2.2 Fabrication

This research employed the hand layup method, a simple and widely used technique for composite fabrication, followed by a mild compression molding step. A release gel was applied to prevent fibers from sticking to mold surface. Thin plastic sheets were used in the top and bottom of mold for a smooth product finish. Bamboo and carbon fiber mats were cut to match the mold size (215 x 215 x 3 mm³). Epoxy resin and hardener were mixed thoroughly in 10:1 ratio for 5 minutes. The mold was closed and subjected to 50 bar pressure in a hydraulic press for curing which lasted approximately 12 hours and the laminate was manufactured as shown in Figure 2. After curing, mold was opened and laminate was removed to cut according to ASTM standards for testing. Composite laminate consists of 9 layers of carbon and bamboo fiber mats to obtain 3mm thickness. The different stacking sequences are as mentioned in Table 2.

Table 2. Specimen designation

Specimen	Sequence of layers (B-bamboo fibre; C-carbon fibre)	Bamboo Fibres (%)
Sample A	B-B-B-B-B-B-B-B	100
Sample B	B-B-B-C-B-C-B-B-B	77.7
Sample C	B-C-B-C-B-C-B-C-B	55.5
Sample D	B-C-C-B-C-C-B-C-C	33.3

Figure 2: a) Mold b) Hydraulic press machine c) Sample Laminated composite

2.3 Mechanical Characterization

Tensile strength & flexural strength tests were performed using Universal testing machine Mecmesin Multi Test 2.5-xt. Laminate composite sample was cut according to ASTM D638-03 for tensile test (specimen dimensions Overall length 115mm Gauge length of 55mm and cross section of 9x3 mm²) and ASTM D790 with specimen dimensions 90mm length and 10x3 mm² cross section for flexural strength determination [27]. Both the tests were carried out at a 10 mm/minute strain rate. For impact resistance analysis, samples were cut according to ASTM D256 with specimen

dimensions 63 x 12.7 x 3 mm³ [28] and Izod impact tests were conducted using computerized testing machine. Impact energy of each specimen was recorded and analyzed. The samples used for tensile testing, flexural testing and impact resistance analysis is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3: a) Tensile testing samples b) Flexural testing samples c) Impact resistance testing samples

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Tensile Test Results of the Laminate Composites

The tensile test results are obtained as recorded in table 3 and the stress vs. strain graph of the bamboo-carbon fibre epoxy laminate composite is shown in Figure 4. It is evident from table 3 and figure 4 that increase in carbon fibre increases tensile strength of hybrid laminated composite. The specimen B which has 22.3% carbon fibre volume fraction showed 128% increase in the ultimate strength compared to Specimen A which has only bamboo fibre reinforcement. Also, the tensile modulus of specimen B is 1190MPa which is much greater than specimen A which is 833 MPa. The specimen C which has 44.5 % carbon fibre volume fraction contributes 54 % increase in the ultimate tensile strength (218 MPa) compared to specimen B (141 MPa). Specimen D with 66.7 % of carbon fibre showed 61 % increase in ultimate tensile strength compared to sample C. When the bamboo fibre is replaced with carbon fibre and as the percentage of carbon fibre increased, there is

increase in tensile strength and tensile module of the composites manufactured. The carbon fibre which has elastic modulus 230 GPa compared to bamboo fibre which has elastic modulus of 85 GPa resulted in significant increase in tensile properties of the samples when percentage of carbon fibre was increased. The tensile modulus showed similar result with increasing percentage of carbon fibre during composite manufacture. Nawras in 2019 showed similar result of increasing mechanical strength, ie. when glass fibre proportion was gradually increased in composite made up of jute fibre and epoxy resin, the tensile strength of the composite increased, tensile strength was approximately equal to 300 MPa in the composite having 70 % glass fibre and 30 % jute fibre which is as same as sample D in which carbon fibre was 66.7 % and bamboo fibre was 33.3 % [29].

Table 3. Tensile test results of bamboo-carbon fibre epoxy laminate composites

Specimen	Break load (N)	Tensile modulus (MPa)	Ultimate tensile strength (MPa)
A	2261	833	62
B	4710	1190	141
C	6560	1428	218
D	7508	2222	351

Figure 4 Stress vs strain curve of bamboo-carbon fibre epoxy laminate composites

3.2 Flexural Test Results of the Laminate Composites

Flexural test results as shown in table 4 indicates increase in flexural strength and flexural modulus with increased carbon layers as we move from sample A to sample D. Force applied vs deformation curve of bamboo-carbon fibre epoxy laminate composites is shown in Figure 5. It is

observed that flexural strength of sample D with 6 layers of carbon fibre is 239.5 MPa which is 36.8 % greater than the sample C which contains only 4 layers of carbon fibre in it. According to the results shown by Shi et al in 2023, the stacking sequence plays a major role in determining strength of composite. They proved that the strength of the laminate deteriorates when the natural fibre forms the outer layers on either side of the laminate composite [23]. Madhu et al in year 2022 proved that the cracks will be initiated on the outer surface if it is natural fibres because of poor interlocking between hydrophilic fibre and hydrophobic resin [30]. In current study, sample B has greater flexural strength compared to sample A inspite of having bamboo fibre laminates on either side is only because of presence of carbon fibre layers inside the composite which gives them higher flexural strength as well as flexural modulus. Sample D with 66.7% of carbon fibre showed maximum flexural strength and flexural modulus of 239.5 MPa and 17900 MPa respectively.

Table 4. Flexural test results of bamboo-carbon fibre epoxy laminate composites

Specimen	Break load (N)	Flexural modulus (MPa)	Ultimate flexural strength (MPa)
A	251	4215	58.3
B	283	7210	115
C	323	9125	175
D	340	17900	239.5

Figure 5 Force applied vs deformation curve of bamboo-carbon fibre epoxy laminate composites

3.3 Impact Test Results of the Laminate Composites

The impact test result is recorded in table 5. Impact strength of sample B is observed to be 19.0 kJ/m² which is almost two times than that of sample A with pure bamboo fibre which is just 10.66 kJ/m². This is because of incorporation of carbon fibre into laminate composite which is having good strength compared to bamboo fibre. Similar result was observed by Zhou et al in year 2020 in which they used bamboo fibre along with glass fibre to form laminate composite, the impact strength of the composite increased with increasing proportion of glass fibre in bamboo-glass fibre reinforced vinyl ester composite [31]. The impact strength of the composite is directly related to the hardness of material, which depends on effective interaction between the fibre and the matrix [32]. As the number of carbon layers increased in laminate composite, the adhesion between fibre layers and epoxy resin was improvised because of which the impact strength of composite increased which is evident in the result obtained for sample B, C and D which is 19.00 kJ/m², 48.61 kJ/m² and 82.06 kJ/m² respectively.

Table 5. Impact test results of bamboo-carbon fibre epoxy laminate composites

Specimen	Energy (kJ)	Impact strength (kJ/m ²)
A	0.48	10.66
B	0.76	19.00
C	1.75	48.61
D	2.67	82.06

Figure 6 Impact strength of bamboo-carbon fibre epoxy laminate composites

4 CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that bamboo/carbon fiber hybrid composites offer tremendous improvements in mechanical properties

compared to pure bamboo composites. With increasing carbon fiber content, the composites exhibit remarkable gains in tensile strength, flexural strength, and impact resistance. Notably, the 40% carbon fiber composite surpasses the tensile strength requirements for specific aerospace applications. Furthermore, even a 13% carbon fiber inclusion offers sufficient strength for automotive components. These findings highlight the potential of bamboo/carbon fiber composites as a viable eco-friendly alternative for structural components in both automobiles and aerospace industries.

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